

Traditional Leadership in the Digital Era as a Balance for Organizational Sustainability

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Abstract

The increasingly complex world demands a leader's adaptability. Technological developments, social life, and culture are undergoing significant changes in various domains. Leaders with self-awareness will serve as role models and balancers within an organization. Such leaders possess superior personal integrity, enabling them to position themselves appropriately, or in Javanese terms, "empan papan."

Traditional leadership has distinctive characteristics according to its context, for example, leadership within the family, leadership in Islamic boarding schools (pesantren), informal leadership in education, and leadership in social organizations. Great leaders possess strong character and competencies.

In today's digital era, the role of leaders dictates the direction of organizational development. In several countries, leaders who have successfully brought progress and maintained their cultural existence are leaders with a global perspective while remaining grounded in local cultural heritage.

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